

**ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ДЕПЕРСОНАЛІЗАЦІЙНО-ДЕРЕАЛІЗАЦІЙНОГО
РОЗЛАДУ КОМОРБІДНОГО З НЕВРОТИЧНИМИ ТА АФЕКТИВНИМИ
РОЗЛАДМИ**

**PECULIARITY OF DEPERSONALIZATION-DEREALIZATION
DISORDER COMORBID WITH NEUROTIC AND AFFECTIVE
DISORDERS**

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Relevance of the topic: depersonalization-derealization disorder (DDD) occurs in approximately 2% of people in the general population. While transient episodes of lifelong depersonalization are common in the general population with a frequency of 26% to 74% (Dewe et al., 2018).

Depersonalization and derealization are the third most common psychiatric symptoms, after anxiety and depression. DDR is more common in comorbid combinations with anxiety and affective disorders, PTSD and personality disorders. In this study, the features of the pathogenetic connection of isolated and comorbid DDR with neurotic and affective disorders are described.

Objective: To investigate the differential diagnostic features of depersonalization and derealization disorders at a young age.

Materials and methods: 29 subjects were divided into four groups: the first group - people with isolated DDR, the second - with comorbid anxiety disorders, the third – with comorbid depressive disorders and the fourth group - people with PTSD. Based on a clinical interview and a block of psychometric scales (Hamilton scale for anxiety assessment, Beck's hopelessness scale; Sheehan's anxiety self-assessment scales, Cambridge Depersonalization Questionnaire, dissociation scales; test of meaning-life orientations in the adaptation by Leontiev, Big Five Inventory) certain

patterns of pathogenetic connection of DDR in the pantry of poverty with neurotic and affective disorders were revealed.

Research results: The adaptive capacity of the group of subjects with isolated DDR and DDR with comorbid PTSD is higher: such individuals are more motivated, have lower rates of depression and anxiety, easier to adapt to the environment despite their symptoms. While the category of subjects with comorbid depression and anxiety is more difficult to tolerate the disease and more focused on symptoms, which often contributes to the exclusion of such patients from social life.

Conclusions: The identified features of the pathogenetic relationship of depersonalization-derealization disorder with neurotic and affective disorders need further study and confirmation by a wider sample of subjects.